

SiC FIBER REINFORCED ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITES: HIGH PRESSURE
SQUEEZE CASTING AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

R. B. Bhagat, M. F. Amateau, J. C. Conway, Jr. and L. S. Harbison
[Engineering Science and Mechanics Department, The Pennsylvania
State University, University Park, PA 16802 USA]

ABSTRACT

Continuous silicon carbide fiber yarn reinforced 6061 aluminum matrix composites have been fabricated by high pressure infiltration casting (HiPIC). A suitable fiber preforming technique is used to fabricate the composites with fiber volume fractions ranging from 0.05 to 0.45. The processing conditions, namely, metal pouring temperature, pressure and pressing time, are optimized to fabricate composites with thorough infiltration and without any casting defects. Microscopic examinations of the cast composites reveal that each fiber tow is thoroughly infiltrated, fibers are uniformly distributed, and there is almost negligible, if any, metallurgical reaction between the fiber and the matrix. Experimental values of the tensile stiffness of the fabricated composites are consistent with those predicted by the rule-of-mixtures (ROM). Results on the ultimate tensile strength and the fracture strain are also presented and discussed. SEM fractographs of the tensile tested composites are included. Failure mechanisms of the fabricated composites are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

High cost of manufacturing near net shape fiber reinforced metal matrix composites is a major reason limiting their commercial applications. In spite of their attractive properties, such as high specific stiffness and strength, and high temperature performance, the metal matrix composites have been by and large used in aerospace and defense applications only. In these applications, improved performance has been the primary consideration, however, cost-effectiveness is a major concern. Several low cost manufacturing techniques for the metal matrix composites have recently been developed based on casting technologies, such as comocasting¹⁻⁸, squeeze casting^{4,5,9-18}, pressure casting¹⁹⁻²¹, investment casting^{22,23}, and high pressure infiltration casting^{18,24-26}. More details on these methods can be found in recent review papers by Bhagat²⁷ and Rohatgi²⁸.

In the present investigation, continuous silicon carbide fiber yarn reinforced 6061 aluminum matrix composites have been fabricated by the high pressure infiltration casting (HiPIC) method. Earlier, this method has been successfully used to fabricate composites with matrices of copper, aluminum, tin or babbitt reinforced with continuous graphite fiber, planar random graphite fiber mat or alumina²⁴⁻²⁶. In the HiPIC method, a relatively high pressure is rapidly applied on the molten metal to effect rapid infiltration of the molten metal into the fiber preform in a metallic die followed by rapid solidification. Bhagat and Amateau²⁹ have demonstrated earlier that the pressure used in the HiPIC method must exceed a threshold pressure, experimentally determined to about 100 MPa to ensure thorough infiltration and to produce cast composites free from shrinkage cavities, gas porosity, and other casting defects. This threshold pressure is defined as the minimum pressure required to circumvent the surface tension effects and allow complete infiltration of the fiber preform. This threshold pressure is also high

enough to cause substantial undercooling and improvement in the heat transfer coefficient. Pressure higher than the threshold pressure further minimizes the contact time between the fiber and the molten metal. Minimum contact time and maximum cooling rate lead to a "clean interface" -- an interface without metallurgical reaction between the fiber and the matrix. The fiber-to-matrix bonding is primarily of adhesion type. The HiPIC method also eliminates the need for fiber coating as well as the need to preheat the die and fiber preform. However, a coated fiber may be used and the coating will remain intact after fabrication.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

1. Composite Fabrication

Continuous multifilament silicon carbide fiber yarn (Nicalon) reinforced 6061 aluminum matrix composite disks, 68 mm or 114 mm diameter by about 4 mm thick have been fabricated by the high pressure infiltration casting (HiPIC) method. The preform is a laminate structure consisting of alternative layers of silicon carbide unidirectional tows and thin planar-random graphite fiber mats. The purpose of the graphite fiber mat is to separate neighboring SiC tows. Two such preforms are needed for each casting. The amount of SiC fiber used in a preform depends on the desired fiber volume fraction in the fabricated composites. A schematic through-the-thickness cross-section of a preform is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Schematic cross-section of a preform of SiC tows and planar random carbon mats.

One preform is placed in the bottom of a metallic die. A measured amount of molten matrix metal (6061 aluminum alloy) is poured into the die over the preform. The second preform is placed in the die followed by top punch and an aligner. This is followed by the rapid application of pressure through the ram of a 1779 KN hydraulic press. Through preliminary experiments, it was found that a temperature of 1125 K and a pressure of 210 MPa were needed for fabricating SiC/6061 aluminum composites with fiber volume fraction ranging from 5 to 45 percent. The pressure is maintained until complete solidification, usually about 60 seconds. This is followed by ram withdrawal and removal of the cast composite from the die. The die and the fiber preform are not preheated in the HiPIC process.

2. Testing and Characterization

The tensile strength and stiffness of the fabricated composites were measured. Rectangular blanks were cut from cast disks with a diamond-tipped saw. These were ground with a carbide disk into dogbone tensile test specimens. Further preparation

of the test specimens required machining the neck and gage sections with a router using carbide tips and polishing with 240- and 320-grit abrasive paper.

A strain gage was bonded to each specimen in the middle of its gage section for the purpose of determining stiffness of the composites. Tensile strength and stiffness tests were carried out on an Instron machine with an 89 LN capacity load cell. Cross-head speed was 0.0085 mm/s. Strain values were read from a strain indicator using a quarter bridge circuit.

Optical and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) were used to characterize the composites. Metallographic examination of polished cross-sections of the specimens was performed to measure the degree of infiltration and the uniformity of the fiber distribution. Fracture surfaces of tensile specimens were examined by SEM to determine the damage mechanisms of the composites, such as fiber pullout, debonding or delamination.

RESULTS

1. Processing

A pressure of 210 MPa and a pouring temperature of 1125 K for 6061 Al resulted in thoroughly infiltrated SiC/6061 Al composites. Figure 2 shows a micrograph of the polished cross-section of a composite with 17 percent fiber volume fraction of silicon carbide fiber. The fiber tows are flattened because of the high pressing pressure. The fiber tow is thoroughly infiltrated by matrix aluminum as evident in Fig. 3. In addition to the circular cross section SiC fibers, graphite fibers can be seen between the SiC tows. These appear as dark elongated shapes. In spite of the generally thorough infiltration, there is occasional fiber contact, as evident at higher magnifications (Fig. 4). The composites are free from casting defects, such as shrinkage cavity and gas porosity.

Fig. 2 Optical micrograph of a cross-section of a SiC/6061 Al unidirectional composite ($V_f = 17$ percent) showing silicon carbide fiber tows.

Fig. 3 Optical micrograph of a fiber tow within the cross-section of a SiC/6061 Al unidirectional composite ($V_f = 17$ percent). Dark elongated shapes within the matrix are carbon fibers.

Fig. 4 Optical micrograph of SiC filaments within a tow from a cross-section of a SiC/6061 Al unidirectional composite ($V_f = 17$ percent) showing occasional fiber contact.

2. Mechanical Properties

Figure 5 shows the Young's modulus of the composites as a function of SiC fiber volume fraction. An effective fiber volume fraction of the planar random graphite fiber mats in the direction parallel to the SiC fibers (equal to one third of the volume fraction of graphite fiber mats) is used in the calculation of the rule of mixtures (ROM) values and is shown as the solid line in Fig. 5. The experimentally determined stiffnesses compare well with those predicted by the ROM relationship over the fiber volume fraction range investigated ($0.08 \leq V_f < 0.40$).

Fig. 5 Plot of Young's modulus of SiC/6061 Al unidirectional composites versus fiber volume fraction showing the increase in modulus with the increase in fiber volume fraction.

The tensile strength of the SiC/6061 Al composites is shown in Fig. 6 as a function of the SiC fiber volume fraction. In general, the tensile strength of the composite increases with an increase in fiber volume fraction. At a fiber volume fraction of 40 percent, the strength of the composite is more than twice the strength of the unreinforced matrix metal cast under identical conditions of the composites. However, the strength values are 67% less than those predicted by the rule-of mixtures. The composites failed at strains of about 0.3 percent.

3. Fracture Mechanisms

The characteristic brittle tensile fracture for the metal matrix composite is seen in Fig. 7. SEM fractographs, shown in Fig. 8(a), clearly indicate that the fibers are pulled out. The surface of the pulled out fibers appears clean as shown in Fig. 8(b). Graphite fibers (from the planar-random mats used in making the preforms) are seen in the SEM fractograph of Fig. 9.

Fig. 6 Plot of the tensile strength of SiC/6061 Al unidirectional composites versus fiber volume fraction showing the increase in strength with the increase in fiber volume fraction.

Fig. 7 Picture showing typical fractured tensile test specimens of SiC/6061 Al unidirectional composites.

Fig. 8 SEM fractographs of a SiC/6061 Al unidirectional composite ($V_f = 28$ percent) showing the relatively clean surfaces of pulled out fibers.

DISCUSSION

The high pressure serves a dual purpose in the fabrication process. First, the pressure forces the molten matrix metal into the fiber preform. Second, immediately following the completion of the infiltration, the rapid application of the pressure raises the solidification temperature of the matrix metal and minimizes the contact resistance with the die wall. As a consequence, the molten matrix rapidly solidifies and the composite cools rapidly enough to prevent excessive fiber/matrix

Fig. 9. SEM fractograph of a SiC/6061 Al unidirectional composite ($V_f = 28$ percent) showing fractured cross-sections of SiC filaments and carbon fibers (long and rod like).

reaction. A pressure of 210 MPa used in the present investigation is suitable to ensure complete infiltration and rapid solidification. The composites are well infiltrated and casting defects were not found in the SiC/6061 Al composites. Fibers are not degraded and the fiber-to-matrix bonding is purely of adhesion type. This observation is supported both by the tensile stiffness results and the cleanliness of the pulled-out fibers in SEM fractographs, see Fig. 8. Though the contact time can be further reduced by increasing the pressure, excessive pressure will flatten the fiber tows and cause fiber-to-fiber contact in the direction of the pressing (see Fig. 4). Such contacts are deleterious to the strength of the composites. The optimum pressing pressure is between the threshold pressure and that which causes excessive fiber contact.

The low measured tensile strength of the composites compared to the rule-of-mixtures strength has not been resolved. The composites failed at a much lower strain (0.3 percent) than the failure strain of the SiC fibers (1.5 percent)³⁰. This indicates that significant embrittlement of the system had occurred. The composites failure mode is a combination of fiber breakage and fiber pull out. SEM fractograph in Fig. 9 shows a possible cause of this embrittlement. It appears that the graphite fibers (from planar-random mats) normal to longitudinal direction of the SiC fibers separate from the matrix at a relatively low tensile load. This separation produces microcracks perpendicular to the loading direction. Microcracks developed during the tensile loading will produce severe stress elevation at the crack tips leading to further cracking of the matrix and breaking of silicon carbide fibers as well. Thus, the composites fail at an external tensile load lower than that predicted by the rule-of-mixtures. The use of planar random mats, therefore, limits the strength which can be obtained. However, significant strengthening is still achieved (see Fig. 6) in the composites fabricated by this method.

CONCLUSIONS

Continuous multifilament silicon carbide reinforced 6061 aluminum composites ($0.05 \leq V_f \leq 0.45$) have been fabricated by a high pressure infiltration

casting (HiPIC) method. Thorough infiltration of the fiber tows is obtained in the cast composites without preheating the fiber preform or the die. Tensile stiffness and strength increase with increasing fiber volume fraction. The stiffness values compare well with those predicted by the rule-of-mixtures. The tensile strength is over twice that of the matrix strength at a fiber volume fraction of 40 percent. However, the tensile strength values are lower than the rule-of-mixture values. The composites fail under tensile loading at a relatively low strain of 0.3 percent. This is attributed to microcracking of the matrix at relatively low applied loads. The site of initial microcracks are assumed to be the locations of graphite fibers lying normal to the loading direction.

REFERENCES

1. Hosking, F. M., Report No. SAND-81-0976, Sandia National Laboratories, Albuquerque, NM (1981), 1-30.
2. Milliere, C. and Suery, M., *Materials Science and Technology*, 4(1) (1988), 41.
3. McCoy, J. W., Jones, C. and Wawner, F. E., *SAMPE Quarterly*, 19(2) (1988), 37.
4. Clegg, A. J., In: *Proceedings of the International Conference on Aluminum Technology '86*, London, England, 11-13 March 1986, Institute of Metals (1986), 731.
5. Gibson, P. R., Clegg, A. J. and Das, A. A., *Mater. Sci. Technol.*, 1(7) (1985), 559.
6. Girot, F. A. et al., In: *ICCM VI and ECCM2*, Vol. 2, Elsevier (1987), 2.330.
7. Gibson, P. R., Clegg, A. J. and Das, A. A., *Foundry Trade J.*, 152(3232) (1982), 262.
8. Bayoumi, M. A. and Suery, M., In: *ICCM VI and ECCM2*, Vol. 2, Elsevier (1987), 2.481.
9. Bhagat, R. B., *Investigation on the Fabrication of Stainless Steel Fiber Reinforced Aluminum Composites*, Ph.D. Thesis, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay, India (1981).
10. Fukunaga, H., Komatsu, S. and Kanoh, Y., *Bull. Japan Soc. Mech. Eng.*, 26 (1983), 1814.
11. Gelderloos, D. G. and Karasek, K. R., *J. Mater. Sci. Letter*, 3 (1984), 232.
12. Bhagat, R. B., In: *ECCM1 - Developments in the Science and Technology of Composite Materials*, AEMC (1985), 610.
13. Bhagat, R. B., In: *Interfaces in Metal-Matrix Composites*, TMS/AIME (1986), 169.
14. Clyne, T. W. and Mason, J. F., *Metallurgical Transactions A*, 18A(8) (1987), 1519.
15. Otori, K. et al., In: *Proceedings of the International Conference on Aluminum Technology 186*, London, 11-13 March 1986, Institute of Metals (1986), 732.
16. Sawada, Y. and Bader, M. G., In: *ICCM V*, TMS/AIME (1985), 785.
17. Clyne, T. W. and Bader, M. G., In: *ICCM V*, TMS/AIME (1985), 755.
18. Bhagat, R. B., *Composites*, 19(5) (1988), 393.
19. Mortensen, A., Cornie, J. A. and Flemings, M. C., *Journal of Metals*, 40(2) (1988), 12.
20. Mortensen, A. and Cornie, J. A., *Metallurgical Transactions A*, 18A(6) (1987), 1160.
21. Nourbakhsh, S., Liang, F. L. and Margolin, H., *Advanced Materials and Manufacturing Processes*, 3(1) (1988), 57.
22. Ahmad, I. and Barranco, J. M., *ARLCB-TR-77036*, Benet Weapons Laboratory (1977), 1-16.
23. McElman, J. A., In: *Engineered Materials Handbook*, Vol. 1 -- Composites, ASM International (1987), 858.
24. Sample, R. J., Bhagat, R. B. and Amateau, M. F., In: *Cast Reinforced Metal Composites*, ASM International (1988), 179.
25. Bhagat, R. B. et al., In: *Cast Reinforced Metal Composites*, ASM International (1988), 185.

26. Sample, R. J. and Bhagat, R. B., Fabrication of Unidirectional Fiber Reinforced 6061 Aluminum Alloy using High Pressure Squeeze Casting, TR-88-015, Applied Research Laboratory, The Pennsylvania State University, University Park, PA (1988), 1-105.
27. Bhagat, R. B., In: Metal Matrix Composites, Academic Press (1989) [in press].
28. Rohatgi, P., In: Metals Handbook (9th edition); Vol. 15, Casting, ASM International (1988), 840.
29. Bhagat, R. B. and Amateau, M. F., High Pressure Casting of Metal Matrix Composites, Presented at Materials Week '87, Cincinnati, OH [pamphlet].
30. Dow Corning's New Product Information Brochure on Nicalon™ Silicon Carbide Fiber (1986).